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Upcycling AlSi10Mg Scrap Metal From Multi-Material Joints Through Atomization And Generation Of Aerospace-Grade Metal Powders

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Abstract

Sustainable disassembly and recovery of end-of-life metal-composite components is a key focus in aviation. Specifically, efficient recycling of metals is hampered by impurity content, which potentially leads to deleterious downgrading of alloys. Recycling of a novel multi-material hybrid joining system for aerospace applications, designed within the EU-funded MIMOSA project, is addressed. The proposed strategy involves mechanical separation of the metal (AlSi10Mg) and composite (CFRP) materials through a multi-stage process. While the CFRP follows a dedicated recycling line, AlSi10Mg is upcycled via atomization to generate sustainable powder feedstock for Additive Manufacturing (AM). Particle size distribution, morphology, chemical composition, tap, and apparent density were evaluated for AlSi10Mg powders from lab-scale atomization. The results confirm the compliance of powder properties with Aerospace standards. Overall, the proposed strategy supports the implementation of a circular model to close the loop on multi-material joints, integrating AM production and recycling of the metal parts of the joints.

Introduction

The global effort towards an increased sustainability of the Aviation and Aerospace sectors faces many challenges, including the reduction of the environmental impact from both manufacturing and processes occurring from the end of the operational life of components. Recycling also has a carbon footprint, which can be taken into account when evaluating sustainability strategies in business cases. For example, incineration may be the cheapest route, but it holds a higher environmental impact. Therefore, both academic and industrial research are focusing on developing processes for recycling composite and specialized alloys (especially those identified as critical raw materials (CRM) [1] to reduce the environmental footprint. With a focused attention developed from the early 2000s, sustainable aircraft manufacturing and recovery of end-of-life components have been at the core of industrial and EU-funded projects aimed at implementing closed-loop recycling strategies [2-5].

From the manufacturing point of view, viable strategies involving Additive Manufacturing (AM) have been implemented in the Aviation and Aerospace sectors to drive further the reduction of their environmental impact [6]. In this view, it is reasonable to argue how to improve the sustainability of the most advanced manufacturing technologies; either by increasing the recycled content in the feedstock for AM or by implementing different techniques to exploit directly specific scrap forms [7]. Considering the economic trends of the AM and metal recycling markets is essential to understand the impact of growing demand for AM components and potential revenues targeting the recycling of retired parts. Based on the most recent data [8, 9], the projected growth of these markets is reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Predicted growth for a) metal AM and metal powders market, and b) global metal recycling market [8,9].

Aluminium alloys are of particular interest in this framework, given their diffuse use in the Aviation and Aerospace sectors for the production of lightweight structures at moderate costs. As an example, focusing on an AM material with significant industrial maturity, such as AlSi10Mg, the global market for this alloy was valued at approximately \$3.1 billion, which is estimated to grow by more than three times by 2030, being the projections set at \$10.6 billion [8,9].

Concerning recycling and recyclability of aluminium alloys, the overall feasibility depends on the chemical composition, with high-purity alloys such as 1070A and 6061 allowing a recycled content higher than 70%, while complex alloys represented for example by alloy 319 and A380 have strict recycling limitations (i.e. recycled content <10%) due to presence of elements such as Cu, Si, and Ni [9]. Moreover, recent studies demonstrated the detrimental effect of impurities on corrosion resistance and mechanical properties of aluminium alloys [11-13], marking the relevance of observing strict tolerances on tramp and alloying elements during the recycling process. Therefore, it is vital to track the streams of materials when applying any of the methodologies which can be classified as upcycling, downcycling or grade maintaining, in order to effectively address the recycling process.

In this context, research and development (R&D) activities conducted within the framework of the MIMOSA project aimed at tackling the intrinsic challenges of recycling aircraft components, to generate new metal and composite feedstock to promote a circular and sustainable manufacturing model. Novel joints developed from this initiative, funded by the EU for the Horizon Europe programme, were considered as a use case to validate an innovative recycling strategy of composite materials. Metal AM and CFRP were joined without the use of metal rivets for increased performance and weight reduction in a vertical stabilizer use case. Afterwards, to simulate after-service decommissioning, metal AM-CFRP joints underwent a multi-step process of separation and reclaiming of useful materials, minimizing waste produced during the recycling process. Whereas CFRP composites were segregated and directed to a dedicated streamline for recovery of fibers, the metal part was retrieved to be recycled through an atomization process. In this way, it was possible to generate new and sustainable powder feedstock for AM. In this case, AlSi10Mg derived from optimization of the AM process to build demonstrators for real-life aircraft components was effectively recycled by maintaining its grade. Additionally, separation trials on metal AM-CFRP joints with simple and complex geometrical features were conducted on an industrial-scale recycling plant already used to recycle up to 100-150 tons per year, to assess the impact of potential contaminations due to the intermixing of scrap flow originating from the Aerospace and Automotive sectors.

This paper will briefly introduce the various steps of the recycling strategy developed within the framework of the MIMOSA project and the results of characterization activities conducted on atomized powders. Proven compliance of the powders with recognized standards for Powder Bed Fusion with Laser Beam (PBF-LB) validates the proposed recycling strategy for metal scrap, representing a first step towards the implementation of a Circular Model within the Aviation and Aerospace sectors.

Materials and Methods

Two different streams of scrap materials were considered for the activities. On the one hand, metal-only samples of AISi10Mg from PBF-LB processes were collected; a) waste material from failed print jobs, b) or calibration specimens used for parameter optimization and validation of mechanical properties constituted the highest fraction of this scrap type, with limited additions of support structures needed to build complex components. Regarding this first kind of scrap, basic treatment of the surface of the parts was conducted by sandblasting and cleaning in an ultrasonic bath with 2-propanol.

Concerning the second case, mechanical recycling was used for the joints. In this case, an industrial single-rotor shredder broke down the multi-material parts to facilitate further steps of separation. Smaller parts with residual CFRPs were subjected to additional separation processes. A hammer-like mill was used to further shred and spheroidize the remaining jointed smaller parts, while parasitic eddy currents were deployed for the separation of the metal from the non-metallic scraps. The final step involved a qualitative densimetric observation of the separated flakes and granulates from polymers and metal, respectively.

AISI10Mg was then post-processed in a laboratory-scale rePowder atomizer (AMAZEMET, Poland). At first, the scrap was loaded in the graphite crucible of an induction melting furnace and heated up to temperatures in the 750-900°C range to achieve full melting and ensure sufficient overheating for the atomization process. Then the liquid metal was cast through a 0.5 mm nozzle onto a plate sonotrode oscillating at 40 kHz. Capillary effects induced by the micrometric displacement of the film of molten metal spread on the plate led to breaking the surface tension of the liquid and the formation of droplets. By cooling down freely in a chamber backfilled with inert gas, micrometric size spherical powders were generated.

Powders were then collected and sieved on woven metal meshes with various sizes to separate oversized particles from powders suitable for AM applications, then to select particles to be used again for PBF-LB processes. A threshold of 150 µm was adopted as the upper limit for AM particles, whereas 77 µm was set to segregate PBF-LB powders. A multi-stage sieve equipped with ultrasonic probes (Assonic, Germany) was employed to suitably size the powder batches.

Further characterization of the powders involved the analysis of relevant chemical and physical properties. Chemical composition was assessed by means of ICP-OES analysis (Thermo Fisher Scientific, United States). Laser diffractometry (Malvern Panalytical, United Kingdom) allowed the measurement of Particle Size Distribution (PSD) of as-atomized powders after removing particles with size larger than 150 µm. Afterwards, ISO-certified laboratory sieves (Giuliani Technologie, Italy) were used to quantify the PSD of PBF-LB powders. With reference to the PBF-LB powder fraction, a Hall Flowmeter (Bettersize, China) was employed to measure the apparent density of the powders according to ASTM B212 standard and flowability according to ASTM B213 standard. Tap density was assessed through an automatic tapper (Bettersize, China) in compliance with ASTM B527. In conclusion, the morphology of the powders was observed by means of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (Zeiss, Germany).

Results and Discussion

AISI10Mg scrap retrieved from the PBF-LB printing activities was collected in various shapes and forms, including plates, machined dog-bone specimens and cubes. Sandblasting was only applied in the specific case of plates previously bonded to CFRP for pull-off tests. After failure of the joints at forces exceeding the bond strength and removal of the CFRP counterpart, residuals of bonding glues and resins were cleared from the metal surface prior to atomization. In any other case, the surface finish was preserved, to assess the impact of native oxides on both as-printed and machined surfaces on the melting and pouring behaviour of AISi10Mg. An overview of the AISi10Mg parts included in this first scrap category is reported below in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Types of PBF-LB processed AlSi10Mg scrap: a) plates bonded to CFRP and used for pull-off tests, b) machined specimens used for tensile tests, c) samples from failed print jobs and density calibration, and d) leftovers from machining 3D printed cylindrical specimens.

Concerning the second source of AlSi10Mg scrap, namely the reclaimed aluminium alloy after the separation process, metal AM-CFRP joints with simplified geometry designed for testing the mechanical strength of the multi-material interface with novel joining technology developed within the MIMOSA project were considered. Samples tested at low load levels to avoid joint failure and spare samples used for metallographic evaluation of bonding at the metal-composite interface were processed as described in the Materials and Methods section, to obtain fine metal granulates, which could then be atomized. The outcome of the separation process was a quantity of particles with variable shapes, from spherical to elongated, and sizes from a few millimetres to 1 cm. Pictures of the parts during different steps of this process are reported below in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Images of a) metal AM-CFRP joints before the separation process, b) metal flakes extracted from treated scrap after shredding, and c) sample of reclaimed metal granulates at the end of the separation process.

Subsequently, after cleaning the surface of the feedstock for atomization with 2-propanol to get rid of organic contaminants, the metal scrap was loaded into the crucible for melting. Energy input was tuned to achieve three targets. First, it was necessary to overcome the melting temperature of AlSi10Mg, which is reported to be around 570°C [14]. In addition, further energy was provided to the metal during melting to overcome heat transfer resistance given by oxidized surfaces and speed up the melting process. Last, overheating was set to ensure that the liquid metal poured on top of the plate sonotrode had a temperature higher than the melting temperature of AlSi10Mg, to avoid instant freezing of the melt. Despite a temperature of 750°C is generally sufficient to ignite the atomization process, the melting temperature of the induction furnace was increased up to 900°C for some of the atomization runs, to overcome poor flowing of the liquid metal through the graphite nozzle of the crucible and to avoid complete clogging of the nozzle opening.

Plates made of high melting temperature alloys ($T_{\text{melt,plate}} > 2 \cdot T_{\text{melt,AlSi10Mg}}$) were employed to atomize AlSi10Mg. These were mounted on an assembly comprising a pressure transducer and a series of extensions to position the plates under the pouring nozzle. The working frequency of the multi-frequency generator equipped with the atomization system could be changed from 20 to 40 kHz. However, to promote the formation of fine particles and target a higher fraction of powders with a lower size, the frequency was

set at 40 kHz, as there is an inverse relationship between those two physical quantities [15]. Examples of the loading of samples inside the crucible and snapshots of both the melting and atomization processes are reported below in Figure 4:

Figure 4. Steps of the ultrasonic atomization process: a) samples loaded in the melting crucible, b) molten AlSi10Mg scrap before casting, and c) liquid AlSi10Mg poured and atomized on the plate sonotrode.

Chemical composition of the atomized powders was assessed separately for both kinds of scrap metal. ICP-OES analysis after digestion of the metal particles in acid solutions was conducted to directly compare the properties of commercial powders and ultrasonically atomized ones. In fact, commercial powders from EOS [16] were used as feedstock for the PBF-LB processes during optimization of the printing parameters for the MIMOSA process. Therefore, it would be reasonable to understand the impact of the recycling process on the chemical properties of atomized AlSi10Mg metal. An overview of the compositional change due to the atomization process is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Chemical composition of AlSi10Mg powders. Comparison among reference form ASTM F3318 standard, commercial powders from EOS, and ultrasonically atomized powders from scrap metal collected from PBF-LB waste or after the metal AM-CFRP joints separation process.

Element	ASTM F3318		AlSi10Mg commercial powders wt. %	Atomized from as-printed AlSi10Mg wt. %	Atomized from reclaimed Al-alloy wt. %
	Min wt. %	Max wt. %			
Cu	-	0.05	< 0.01	0.030 ± 0.004	3.97 ± 0.30
Fe	-	0.55	0.19	0.17 ± 0.03	0.338 ± 0.050
Mg	0.20	0.45	0.32	0.29 ± 0.02	0.217 ± 0.016
Mn	-	0.45	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.014 ± 0.004
Ni	-	0.05	0.01	0.006 ± 0.002	0.031 ± 0.008
Si	9.0	11.0	9.5	9.5 ± 0.6	9.0 ± 0.5
Zn	-	0.10	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.417 ± 0.032
Ti	-	0.15	0.01	0.006 ± 0.002	0.032 ± 0.008
Pb	-	0.05	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
Sn	-	0.05	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.058 ± 0.015
Other (each)	-	0.05	< 0.05	< 0.15	< 0.15
Other (total)	-	0.15	< 0.15	< 0.05	< 0.05
Al	Balance		Balance	Balance	Balance

Chemical composition of the commercial powders was reported from the certificate of conformance of the printed powder batch. For atomized powders, on the other hand, results of laboratory analysis have been added to the table. Moreover, all the different conditions are compared with the prescription from ASTM F3318 "Standard for Additive Manufacturing – Finished Part Properties – Specification for AlSi10Mg with Powder Bed Fusion – Laser Beam" [17], which is globally recognized for AM components to be deployed in the Aerospace sector. It is worth mentioning that the chemical composition is still compliant with ASTM standard for powders atomized from scrap metal sourced from PBF-LB waste material, despite a minor loss of Mg. On the other hand, analysis of the powders atomized from reclaimed aluminium alloy after the

separation process of the metal AM-CFRP joints highlighted a few discrepancies, mainly involving increased content of Cu, Fe and Zn, together with slightly more pronounced Mg losses. In particular, Cu and Zn concentrations were higher than compositional limits set by the reference standard. This may be explained by potential contamination of the reclaimed alloy with residuals of other Al-Cu and Al-Zn alloys previously processed during the recycling. The assumption is that even though a deep cleaning step was conducted prior to the prime separation trial, it was possible that residual traces of other alloys were still present, given the complexity of the industrial machinery. Even though, it can be argued a risk of contamination, additional optimization of the cleaning steps can easily be applied, or an exclusive use of machinery for admitting AlSi10Mg input can be considered for the reduction and/or elimination of the contamination levels. Regarding the physical properties of the atomized powders, some observations could be made from the analysis of particles after sieving with metal meshes. Specifically, a threshold of 150 μm was adopted to separate the particles with larger dimensions, which were deemed to be oversized or too irregular for AM applications. The powder yield, defined as the weight ratio between in-spec powders and the amount of process feedstock, was 53.95% and 63.37% for as-printed AlSi10Mg and reclaimed Al-alloy, respectively. At this point, laser diffractometry was adopted to evaluate the PSD of as-atomized powders with a size lower than 150 μm . The result of the analysis of a representative batch of powders is reported below in Figure 5:

Figure 5. Particle size distribution of the as-atomized powders observed by means of laser diffractometry. Volumetric frequency distribution is reported with the red curve, whereas the cumulative distribution is plotted in green colour.

It can be noted that the frequency distribution curve is narrow, with sizes centred around the value of 76.1 μm for the average diameter of the equivalent spheres observed by the laser diffractometer. Clearly, this kind of distribution could not be applicable to conventional PBF-LB processes.

Therefore, a further sieving step with a metal mesh with a nominal opening size of 77 μm was adopted, yielding more than 50% of powders over the total amount of particles with sizes below 150 μm .

The powders going through the 77 μm mesh were retrieved and tested for relevant physical properties. ISO-certified meshes were used for determining the PSD, whereas flowability was measured by means of a Hall flowmeter. Apparent and Tap densities were assessed as well, and an overview of the results is reported below in Table 2:

Table 2: Physical properties of commercial and ultrasonically atomized powders.

Powder sample	Particle Size Distribution			Hall Flowability	Apparent Density	Tap Density
	D ₁₀ [μm]	D ₅₀ [μm]	D ₉₀ [μm]	[s/50g]	[g/cm ³]	[g/cm ³]
AlSi10Mg commercial powders	20 – 33*	38 – 53*	63 – 80*	N/A	1.10 – 1.50	1.40 – 1.80
Atomized from as-printed AlSi10Mg	42.2	53.6	62.8	46.1	1.47	1.67
Atomized from reclaimed Al-alloy	36.2	51.0	61.4	44	1.52	1.72

* Particle size distribution is reported from the certificate of conformance of commercial powders, as measured by laser diffractometry. Hall flowability of the commercial powders was not available (N/A).

It can be observed that only minor differences could be detected between commercial and ultrasonically atomized powders. The value of D_{10} of both the ultrasonically atomized batches was higher than typical ones for commercial gas atomized powders, due to the sharp cut of the original distribution of the particles generated by the sonotrode oscillations at 40 kHz, whereas the D_{50} and D_{90} values fell within the typical ranges of gas atomized powders. Hall flowability was reported for ultrasonically atomized powders to demonstrate that the particles are free-flowing and thus can be spread uniformly inside the PBF-LB printer during recoating of the powder bed. This property is of paramount importance, as a dense powder bed is the basis for building fully dense and crack-free parts during the AM process. Additionally, values for Apparent and Tap density were as well in line with those expected from commercial gas atomized powders. The latter considerations about flowability were supported by the morphological analysis of the particles. Indeed, SEM images (Figure 6) demonstrate that the atomized powders are highly spherical with an extremely low fraction of satellites. Few elongated particles and/or agglomerates are still present after removing the powders with a size bigger than 150 μm , as shown in Figure 6 c) and d). However, since those particles had dimensions in the 100-120 μm range, they were more likely removed during the second sieving stage and were excluded from the powder batch to be processed by PBF-LB.

Figure 6. Morphology of ultrasonically atomized particles observed by SEM: a) spherical particles at lower magnification, b) spherical particles at higher magnification, c) close-up of agglomerated particles, and d) close-up of elongated particles.

Conclusions

This study presents the experimental work related to AlSi10Mg powders produced through ultrasonic atomization. Two different streams of secondary sourced metal generated within the framework of the MIMOSA project were addressed. The impact of the scrap preparation is mainly focused on the separation step of the recycling process of the innovative metal AM-CFRP joints. It can be concluded that the ultrasonic atomization process is a viable method to generate sustainable powders for PBF-LB manufacturing, with chemical properties in accordance with aerospace-grade quality defined by industrial standards and physical properties in line with those of commercially available gas-atomized powders. The relevance of potential contaminations derived from the recycling process conducted on an industrial size plant was

evaluated at the chemical level, and considerations on how to mitigate the related degradation risks were discussed.

Overall, the research related to this study is a fundamental step to promote the use of AM feedstock from recycled metals. The results from PBF-LB print jobs with recycled AISi10Mg powders and their subsequent mechanical and physical evaluation have been planned for a later stage in the MIMOSA project, whereas the assessment of savings with respect to environmental impact carried using virgin powders atomised from raw materials would be the next step to complete the analysis. In addition, it must be underlined that the results of the validation of the proposed recycling strategy would be the basis to implement a more structured circular model in the Aerospace sector, involving the recycling of aircraft components and AM, and aiming eventually at a closed-loop strategy to maintain the grade of specific alloys. Last but not least, such a model could be easily extended to other alloys such as titanium and nickel-based alloys, tackling the current challenges of the market, such as the EU's sustainability targets for critical raw materials, supply chain gaps and recent trade burdens.

References

- [1] European Commission (2024), REGULATION (EU) 2024/1252 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 11 April 2024, establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1252/oj>. Accessed: 20 April 2025.
- [2] Alcoa to recycle aluminium scrap of Boeing aeroplanes, Web article, <https://www.airport-technology.com/uncategorized/newsalcoa-to-recycle-aluminium-scrap-of-boeing-aeroplanes/>. Accessed: 10 April 2025.
- [3] Sustainable Dismantling and Recycling of Metallic Aerostructures, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/632487>. Accessed: 12 April 2025.
- [4] European recycling and circularity in large composite components, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/632487>. Accessed: 12 April 2025.
- [5] Ramawat N, Sharma N, Yamba P, Sanidhi MA. Recycling of polymer-matrix composites used in the aerospace industry-A comprehensive review. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 2023 Jun 3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.05.386>.
- [6] Alami AH, Olabi AG, Alashkar A, Alasad S, Aljaghoub H, Rezk H, Abdelkareem MA. Additive manufacturing in the aerospace and automotive industries: Recent trends and role in achieving sustainable development goals. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*. 2023 Nov 1;14(11):102516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2023.102516>.
- [7] Yakubov V, Ostergaard H, Bhagavath S, Leung CL, Hughes J, Yasa E, Khezri M, Lösckke SK, Li Q, Paradowska AM. Recycled aluminium feedstock in metal additive manufacturing: A state of the art review. *Heliyon*. 2024 Mar 3. 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e27243.
- [8] Precedence Research. <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/>. Accessed: 8 April 2025.
- [9] Grand View Research. <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/>. Accessed: 8 April 2025.
- [10] Raabe D, Ponge D, Uggowitz P, Roscher M, Paolantonio M, Liu C, Antrekowitsch H, Kozeschnik E, Seidmann D, Gault B, De Geuser F. Making sustainable aluminum by recycling scrap: The science of “dirty” alloys. *Progress in materials science*. 2022 Jul 1;128:100947. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2022.100947>.
- [11] Sainis S, Persson D, Törne K, Tidblad J, Thierry D. The influence of recycling on the localized corrosion susceptibility of extruded AA6063 alloys. *npj Materials Degradation*. 2024 Sep 10;8(1):95. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41529-024-00510-5>.
- [12] Gao Y, Li Y, Hao W, Li Y, Xie J, Zhao Y, Zhang X. Effect of quenching protocols on microstructure and corrosion morphology in a recycled Al–Mg–Si alloy: Tracing Cu impurities. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*. 2024 Nov 1;33:3965-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2024.10.099>.
- [13] Kuchariková L, Pastierovičová L, Tillová E, Uhrčík M, Zatkalíková V, Šajgalík M. The Influence of a Corrosive Environment on Fatigue and Mechanical Properties of An Al-Cast Alloy with Higher Fe Content. *Metals*. 2023 May 25;13(6):1019. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13061019>.
- [14] AISi10Mg, As-built Aluminium Alloy, <https://apm.matweb.com/search/datasheet.aspx?matguid=4501b3b8259e4767ad9248ed98e70fb6&ckck=1>. Accessed: 2 April 2025
- [15] Yasuda K, Honma H, Xu Z, Asakura Y, Koda S. Ultrasonic atomization amount for different frequencies. *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*. 2011 Jul 20;50(7S):07HE23. DOI 10.1143/JJAP.50.07HE23.
- [16] Aluminium for Industrial 3D Printing, EOS website, <https://www.eos.info/metal-solutions/metal-materials/aluminium#eos-aluminium-alsi10mg>. Accessed: 10 April 2025.
- [17] F3318 Standard for Additive Manufacturing – Finished Part Properties – Specification for AISi10Mg with Powder Bed Fusion – Laser Beam. <https://store.astm.org/f3318-18.html>. Accessed: 10 April 2025.

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